

Modeling and Simulation Study on High-Efficiency Triple Junction Solar Cells: Optimizing Design Parameters for InGaP/GaAs/Ge

Paper Id : 19137 Submission Date : 2024-07-12 Acceptance Date : 2024-07-22 Publication Date : 2024-07-25
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DOI:10.5281/zenodo.13374186

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Abstract

A significant advancement in photovoltaic technology, high-efficiency triple-junction solar power cells improve efficiency by utilizing three semiconductor materials to capture a broader range of sunlight. The most challenging aspect of working with these semiconductors, such as indium gallium phosphide (InGaP), gallium arsenide (GaAs), and germanium (Ge), is finding the optimal balance between different design factors. This paper aims to develop methods to increase energy conversion efficiency and establish the foundation for improved and more durable solar energy solutions by optimizing the performance of triple-junction (3J) solar cells under varying temperatures. The results demonstrated that these variables have a significant impact on the performance of solar cells in terms of electrical output and overall efficiency. As the temperature increases from 300 K to 400 K, the values of the parameters vary according to V_{oc} (2.868 V), J_{sc} (20.45 mA/cm²), V_{max} (2.801 V), J_{max} (19.821 mA/cm²), P_{max} (52.4567 mW/cm²), Fill Factor (89.4341%), and Efficiency (41.9653%) These findings demonstrate a noteworthy advancement in solar energy technologies that improve sustainability and efficiency by optimizing different parameters and investigating novel approaches. The study also contributes to the ongoing development of photovoltaic systems

Keywords Renewable Energy, Triple Junction, Solar Power, Semiconductors, Photovoltaic System.

Introduction

The sun is a significant source of energy on Earth's surface. The earth receives approximately 1000W/m² of solar energy daily. This amount of sunlight has the potential to generate around 8500 TW of energy globally. As global energy demands continue to rise, solar photovoltaics play a crucial role in meeting those demands [1]. In solar photovoltaics, performance is the most crucial factor to consider, as weather and light intensity are not consistently stable when used on land. Researchers are focusing on developing affordable and more efficient solar power devices [2]. The advancement of science and technology has led to the development and utilization of solar cells, or photovoltaic devices, for electricity generation through the principle of electronic radiative conversion. Solar cells are important devices designed to harness solar energy, providing a source of clean, renewable energy that could be utilized repeatedly [3]. Solar power has become a crucial renewable energy source that could significantly impact the future of energy production. Solar cells that convert light energy into electricity are categorized into different generations based on their materials and assembly methods [4][5]. In real-world conditions, humidity and temperature could reduce the stability of solar cells by affecting photoelectric and material characteristics [6]. However, simple steps have successfully

manufactured high-efficiency Ga InP/Ga As/InGa As solar cells. These steps include applying a thin metal film to a flexible substrate, etching the Ga As substrate, and temporarily connecting the two [7]. It's essential to conduct more rapid ageing tests to ensure the reliability of the process and the stability of flexible solar power cell performance. Currently, thin-film solar cells are the most commonly researched option due to their superior performance and lower cost [8]. Over the past few years, there has been significant research interest in micro-thin-film solar panels because of their lightweight nature, which is crucial for applications in space. Cadmium telluride (CdTe), amorphous silicon (a-Si), copper indium diselenide (CIS), and gallium arsenide (Ga As) are some thin-film light-absorbing semiconductor solar cell designs [9-10]. Ga As is a light-absorbing semiconductor from the III/V compound semiconductor and is the most efficient semiconductor in the world. At the Sandia (3/99) test centre, thin-film m-Si solar cells showed an efficiency of 25.0% ($\pm 0.5\%$ tolerance). At Atla Device in the USA/New York, thin-film Ga As solar cells showed an efficiency of 29.1% (± 0.6 tolerance). Germanium heterojunction solar cells are 7.9% efficient at their best.

Multi-junction solar cells (MJSCs) could produce approximately twice the power of a regular solar cell of the same size [11]. They are a superior choice due to their cost-effectiveness, higher power generation efficiency, and increased theoretical conversion efficiency compared to other photovoltaic technologies. Two types of MJSCs were evaluated: InGa P-Ga As dual-junction solar panels with InGa P tunnelling layers and InGa P-Ga As-Ge triple-junction solar panel cells with Ga As tunnelling layers [12]. Recent studies indicate that triple junction (3J) solar panels have achieved over 44% efficiency, with expectations of reaching 50% efficiency for 4 to 5 -junction solar panel cells. Semiconductors such as Ge, Ga InAs/Ga As, and Ga InP are widely utilized in triple-junction solar cells due to their efficient light absorption and suitable minority carrier lifetimes and mobilities [13]. In a triple-junction solar cell, the first layer (Ga InP) absorbs the short-range portion of the spectrum, the second layer (Ga InAs) captures near-infrared light, and the third layer (Ge) absorbs the lower energy levels of infrared radiation. InGa P/Ga As/Ge triple-junction solar cells could function more effectively in space by reducing the wide band gap of the middle cell [14]. In a triple-junction solar cell model using InGa P, Ga As, and Ge, the heterojunction of two different semiconductor components could only occur if their lattice constants were very close to each other [15].

The traditional methods typically include experimental fabrication and testing for optimizing high-efficiency triple junction solar cells. This involves creating physical prototypes of solar cells with various material configurations and layer thicknesses, testing their electrical output, efficiency, and durability under different lighting conditions, and using techniques like X-ray diffraction (XRD), scanning electron microscopy (SEM), and photoluminescence (PL) for material characterization [16-17]. Studying the modelling and simulation of high-efficiency triple junction solar cells is important for advancing solar energy technology [18]. This research focuses on optimizing design parameters for InGa P/Ga As/Ge to maximize efficiency. High-efficiency triple junction solar cells have the potential to significantly increase the conversion of sunlight into electricity, thus making solar power more viable and competitive with traditional energy sources [19].

The study faces limitations in simulation accuracy, material quality variations, and environmental factors. Simulations could not capture all real-world phenomena, leading to discrepancies between simulated and actual performance [20]. Variations in material quality (InGa P, Ga As, Ge) and unconsidered environmental factors (temperature, radiation, mechanical stress) could impact solar cell performance and durability affecting the accuracy of the simulation results.

Designing and optimizing triple-junction solar cells is highly complex. It involves multiple factors such as bandgap alignment, lattice matching, and layer thickness [21]. Accurately estimating material properties is challenging, and limitations in simulation software affect the reliability of models and require significant computational resources. Validation with experimental data is crucial but difficult. Material variability and interlayer defects could impact performance while managing heat dissipation is critical for efficiency [22]. Scalability and maintaining cost-efficiency in large-scale production are significant challenges for the economic viability of optimized designs.

This research focuses on optimizing design parameters for InGa P/ Ga As/Ge to maximize efficiency by using computational methods, this study aims to rapidly identify the best configurations, reducing the time and cost associated with traditional experimental

approaches. High-efficiency triple junction solar cells have the potential to significantly increase the conversion of sunlight into electricity, making solar power more viable and competitive with traditional energy sources. This research not only enhances the scientific understanding of multi-junction solar cells but also supports the development of more effective and affordable renewable energy solutions, crucial for addressing global energy demands and mitigating the impacts of climate change.

Objective of study

These are the research objectives for this research:

1. Conduct a comprehensive literature review of Triple Junction (TJ) solar cell designs.
2. Run simulations using the proper Silvaco Advanced Technology Laboratory for Analysis and Simulation (ATLAS) software tools to mimic real-world circumstances and see how the TJ solar cell performs with various parameters.
3. To increase productivity and comprehension of the effects of altering the bottom cell, top cell, and medium cell material.

This research has the following research contributions:

1. The research is performed to identify optimal design parameters for high-efficiency triple junction solar cells.
2. The research explored the insight into the electrical and optical behaviours of Indium Gallium Phosphide (InGaP), Gallium Arsenide (GaAs), and Germanium (Ge) layers.
3. The research contributes to the advancement of solar cell technology through computational modelling and simulation.
4. The research explored the potential for improving the scalability and cost-effectiveness of solar energy solutions.

The next parts of this work are structured in the following manner: The next section offers the relevant studies of various authors. Section III details the methodology for High-Efficiency Triple Junction Solar Cells: Optimizing Design Parameters for InGaP/GaAs/Ge. Section IV presents the simulation results, including performance analysis. Finally, Section V provides a conclusion of the outcomes of this study and outlines potential areas for further investigation.

Review of Literature

In this section, previous studies on the modelling and simulation of InGaP/GaAs/Ge solar cells are reviewed, which highlighting several critical parameters.

Kharchich et al., (2024) [23] utilized a dual-junction solar cell optimization technique made from GaAs and GaSb to determine the ideal parameters for the uppermost base layer, which was the most effective method for absorbing the full spectrum of solar radiation. In the standard AM1.5G spectrum, they were able to get a power conversion efficiency of 41.65%, an open circuit voltage of 1.78V, a short circuit current of 235.72 mA/cm², and a fill factor of 90.16%.

Eddin et al., (2023) [24] enhanced the performance of a homojunction GaAs solar panel using the Silicon Valley Corporation (SILVACO) model by incorporating a p-InGaP layer for the front surface field (FSF) and an n-AlGaInP layer for the back surface field (BSF). The finding showed that the basic cell achieved an efficiency of 7.82% to increase the efficiency by 21.09%, it was recommended to add a p-InGaP layer to the standard cell. Similarly, the basic cell utilizing the n-AlGaInP layer achieved an efficiency of 16.09%, while the best cell incorporating both FSF and BSF layers achieved an efficiency of 30.88%. The improved efficiency of cells with p-InGaP and n-AlGaInP layers was attributed to higher photon absorption and photogeneration rates.

Zakarya et al (2023) [25] utilized Silvaco Technology Computer-Aided Design (TCAD) tools to enhance a 5-junction cell that was comprised of AlInP, AlGaInP, AlGaInAs, GaInP, GaAs, and InGaAs, as well as Ge, which was the most efficient photovoltaic technology currently available in multi-junction solar cells, which were composed of stacked III-V semiconductor junctions. Recent tests have demonstrated that these cells were more than 47% efficient. The efficiency was determined by simulating the spectral

absorption and I -V characteristics for each semiconductor mix and identifying the best thickness set to achieve a 26% performance under one sun .

Xu et al., (2023) [26] utilized the electroluminescence (EL) technique to measure the minority carrier lifespan of each Inverted Metamorphic Multi-Junction (IMM3J) solar cell subcell before and after exposure to 2 MeV protons. Before the exposure, the Ga InP, Ga As, and InGa As subcells had minority carrier lifetimes of 6.99×10^{-9} s, 3.09×10^{-8} s, and 2.31×10^{-8} s, respectively. After the proton treatment, the minority carrier lifetimes in the Ga InP, Ga As, and InGa As subcells significantly decreased by 1.63×10^{-10} s, 1.56×10^{-11} s, and 1.65×10^{-10} s, respectively. These results indicate that the short-circuit power and open-circuit voltage for each subcell would decrease over time.

Aissat et al, (2021) [27] utilized triple junction technology composed of InGa P, InGa As, and Ge, which focused on simulating and enhancing the electrical and structural properties of highly efficient solar cells. The result showed that the open-circuit voltage reached 2.3 V and the short-circuit current reached 20 mA/cm², with a fill factor of 81.73% and a conversion efficiency of 39.03, where. the overall performance increased by 18%.

Salem et al., (2021) [28] employed a Single Large Vertical Cavity Surface Emitting Laser Array Technology Computer-Aided Design (SLVACO TCAD) tool to carry out all the optimization steps and simulation data for improving the performance of the InGa P/Ga As dual-junction (DJ) solar cells and enhanced the performance of the Dual-Junction (DJ) solar cell using two different top window materials, AlGa As and AlGa InP. As a result, AlGa InP emerged as the superior material for the top window layer of the InGa P/Ga As DJ cell, providing a 4% increase in conversion efficiency under one sun of the typical AM1.5G solar spectrum at 300 K, compared to recent research.

Li et al., (2020) [29] investigated the effects of proton exposure on Ga InP/Ga As/Ge triple-junction solar panels with varying Ga As sub-cell emitter thicknesses. The results showed that proton exposure caused more damage to the external quantum efficiency of the Ga As sub-cell compared to the Ga InP sub-cell and the study observed that as the emitter thickness increased after proton irradiation, the external quantum efficiency of the Ga As sub -cell initially increased and then decreased.

Zhang et al., (2020) [30] developed a TiO₂/Al₂O₃/MgF₂ multilayer anti-reflective (AR) coating using an Electron Beam Evaporation (EBE) system with 1 MeV electron beam irradiation. to optimize the performance of a Ga InP/Ga As/Ge triple-junction solar panel. The TiO₂/Al₂O₃/MgF₂ multi-layer AR coating has the potential to improve the triple junction solar cell's resistance to radiation by enhancing permeability across a wide range of wavelengths, particularly in the 750–900 nm region, which was the primary degradation window for the triple junction solar panels.

Gahouch et al. (2020) [31] utilized duplicated junction solar cells to create a concentrated photovoltaic (CPV) system that could reduce costs and improve efficiency. The results indicate that duplicated junction designs could enhance the efficiency of III-V solar cells at high levels, exceeding 1000 suns (under the AM1.5D spectrum of the sun at 300 K), and a cost analysis shows that these designs could reduce costs at ultra -high concentrations (UHCs) by over 30%.

Methodology

This study employs a computational research design to optimize the design parameters of high -efficiency triple junction solar cells consisting of Indium Gallium Phosphide (InGa P), Gallium Arsenide (Ga As), and Germanium (Ge) layers.

Statistics Used in the Study

Material Properties

Conventional silicon solar cells would gradually be replaced by high-efficiency multi-junction solar cells on space solar generators because of the growing need for power, mass, and area. To achieve high efficiency by current matching among the produced current from each sub-cell, band gap energy should be rigorously joined. TJ solar cells are made up of sub-cells, namely Ga InP, Ga As, and Ge junctions, which are coupled in series in a manner that

is comparable to the traditional one [32]. A window, a p-n junction, a Back Surface Field (BSF) layer, and a buffer layer are the components that make up the top Ga InP cells, the middle Ga As cells, and the bottom Ge cells, respectively. For the simulation, they used InGa P, Ga As, and Ge materials, and their properties are provided in Table 1. The TJ design in a PV is shown in [33–34].

Table 1: Material properties of these materials

Cathode			
N-AlInGaP	Window	0.03 μm	Top Cell GaInP
N-GaInP	Emitter	0.03 μm	
P-GaInP	Base	0.68 μm	
P-GaInP	BSF	0.05 μm	
P-Tunnel Junction		0.01 μm	Tunnelling junction
N-Tunnel Junction		0.01 μm	
N-AlGaAs	Window	0.1 μm	Middle Cell GaAs
N-GaAs	Emitter	0.1 μm	
P-GaAs	Base	2.5 μm	
P-GaAs	BSF	0.03 μm	
P-Tunnel Junction		0.01 μm	Tunnelling junction
N-Tunnel Junction		0.01 μm	
N-InGaP	Window	0.01 μm	Bottom Cell Ge
N-Ge	Emitter	0.3 μm	
P-Ge	Substance	0.15 μm	
Anode			

Table 2 shows the values of the material parameters.

Table 2: Values of The Material Parameters

Parameters	In GaP	GaAs	Ge
Band gap (eV)	1.90	1.42	0.66
Electron mobility (cm ² /Vs)	1945	8800	3900
Hole mobility (cm ² /Vs)	141	400	1900
Permittivity (ε)	11.6	13.1	16
Lattice constant (A ⁰)	5.63	5.65	5.68

An illustration of the equivalent circuit of a TJ solar cell could be seen in Figure 1, which could be found below:

Figure 1: Electric circuit representation of a TJ solar cell [35].

The corresponding electrical circuit provides the following equation (1) for the total current density.

$$J_L = J_{sc,i} - J_{o,i} \left[\exp\left(\frac{q(V_i + AR_{s,i}J_L)}{n_i K_B T}\right) - 1 \right] \frac{V_i + AR_{s,i}J_L}{AR_{sh,i}} \quad (1)$$

Where i , J_{sc} , J_o , J_L , q , V , R_{sh} , R_s , K_B , n , A , T characterize the number of sub-cells (1=high, 2=medium, and 3=low), photon current density in A/cm^2 , reverse saturation current density in A/cm^2 , operating current density of cell in A/cm^2 , electrical charge constant, operating voltage per cell in V , shunt resistance in Ω , series resistance in Ω , Boltzmann constant, cell area in cm^2 , diode ideality factor, cell area in cm^2 and operating temperature in K correspondingly [36]. The uniformity of the cell's temperature is assumed. A direct relationship between temperature and the dark saturation current of a diode could be expressed as follows [37]:

$$J_{o,i} = k_i \times T^{-3+\gamma_i} \times e^{\frac{-q \times E_{gi}}{k_B \times T}} \quad (2)$$

The Boltzmann constant is denoted by K_B , the band gap energy is given by E_g in eV, and γ_i is a constant. As a result of material differences, band gap energy varies between cells. Here is equation 3 which describes the relationship between E_g and temperature:

$$E_{gi} = E_g(0) - \frac{\alpha_i \times T^2}{T + \sigma_i} \quad (3)$$

The E_g at $0^\circ C$, denoted as $E_g(0)$, is determined by the materials utilized, together with the constants α and σ . InGaAs and InGaP mixed alloys have a significant impact on the band gap energy as stated in equation (4). However pure products containing Germanium, abbreviated "Ge,"

$$E_{gi}(A_{1-x}B_x) = (1-x)E_g(A) + xE_g(A) + xE_g(B) - x(1-x)P \quad (4)$$

In this context, $A_{1-x}B_x$ denotes the alloy materials' composition, and P is an alloy-dependant parameter that considers eV -scale deviations from the linear approximation. By adding the voltages of the three series-connected sub-cells, the equation for the voltage at the terminals of a TJ solar cell could be expressed [38].

$$V = \sum_{i=1}^3 V_i \quad (5)$$

Where,

$$V_i = \frac{n_i K_B T}{q} \ln \left[\frac{J_{sc,i} - J_L}{J_{o,i}} + 1 \right] - J_L A R_{s,i} \quad (6)$$

V_i : Voltage of the i -th cell or layer, n_i : Ideality factor of the i -th cell or layer, K_B : Boltzmann constant, T : Temperature in Kelvin, q : Charge of an electron, $J_{sc,i}$: Short-circuit current density of the i -th cell or layer, J_L : Light-generated current density, $J_{o,i}$: Saturation current density of the i -th cell or layer, $A R_{s,i}$: Series resistance area factor of the i -th cell or layer.

The following equation describes the V_{oc} per cell, which is obtained by cancelling the operating current density J_L .

$$V = \frac{n_i K_B T}{q} \ln \left[\frac{J_{sc,i}}{J_{o,i}} + 1 \right] \quad (7)$$

The maximum power point "MPP" is produced by cancelling the equation dP/dJ_L where $P = J_L V A$, and the V_{oc} is inversely proportional to temperature. This could be shown using the characteristics illustration of the I-V curve [39]

Simulation Model

The TJ solar cell was numerically simulated using SILVACO-ATLAS Software (Deck Editor Version 4.2.5.R) in this research. The program was created by SILVACO International and is a tool for physically based solar simulators [40]. The Finite Element Method (FEM) serves as the foundation for this method of analysis, which allows engineers to forecast the electrical and optical properties of semiconductor devices that have been described. By using Newton-linked and Gummel-decoupled approaches via a two-dimensional grid. The Poisson equation, the continuity equation, and the transport equation are all included in these equations, which are derived from Maxwell's equations [41]. There is a wide selection of physical models available to choose from inside the software to describe physical processes [42]. Three of ATLAS's several physics-based models' concentration dependent mobility (CONMOB), Shockley-Read-Hall (SRH), and Optical Recombination model (OPTR) are among the most accurate available [43].

SRH Recombination

Fixed lifetimes are used to specify Shockley Red Hall (SRH) recombination.

$$R_{SRH} = \frac{p_n - n_{ie}^2}{\tau_{AU0}[p + n_{ie} \exp(\frac{-ETRAP}{kTL})] + \tau_{AU0}[p + n_{ie} \exp(\frac{-ETRAP}{kTL})]} \tag{8}$$

Where ETRAP is the energy gap between the trap and intrinsic Fermi levels, kTL is the Kelvin temperature of the lattice, τ_{AU0} and τ_{AU0} are the lifetimes of electrons and holes, p and n are the densities of holes and electrons, and n_{ie} is the intrinsic carrier density [44]. The SRH parameter of the model's statement is used to activate this model. In the material declarations, the electron and hole lifespan parameters, τ_{AU0} and τ_{AU0} , are user definable.

OPTR Model

The OPTR model, which could be expressed as

$$R_{auger} = AUGN(pn^2 - n_{ie}^2) + AUGP(np^2 - n_{ie}^2) \tag{9}$$

Where p , n , and n_{ie} are defined in the previous section, and AUGN and AUGP are user-defined variables with default values of $8.3e-32$ cm⁶/s and $1.8e-31$ cm⁶/s, respectively. The Band Gap Narrowing model (BGN) model is used here. Neither the narrow bandgap model nor Klaassen's temperature-dependent model is considered [45].

CONMOB Model

The usage of a CONMOB model for gallium arsenide and silicon is specified. This model is a mobility versus doping table that is only valid for 300K. The top layer and substrate are solved using this model. The final current calculation also includes solving the Fermi level and models for fixed Fermi. Within the framework of the drift-diffusion model, the simulator determines the solutions to the fundamental Poisson equation and the continuity equation about electrons and holes independently. The optical simulator considers Fresnel's reflection, refraction, and transmission while simulating the creation of electrons and holes by incoming light [46].

Flow of Proposed Model

The construction of a TJ solar cell is made up of three layers of semiconductors: the top layer is made up of Ga InP, the middle layer is made up of Ga As, and the bottom layer is made up of Ge. Specifically, these layers have been carefully designed to effectively absorb various components of the sun spectrum, which ultimately results in improved solar cell efficiency as a whole. Figure 2 presents a flow diagram of the suggested extraction process, which is provided in this section.

Figure 2: Flowchart of the proposed extraction method

Step 1: This stage illustrates the architectural design of the TJ solar cell. The cells composed of Ga As, Ge, and GaInP are visible in a vertical arrangement.

Step 2: The SILVACO-ATLAS software is used to determine and collect the material characteristics of Ga InP, Ga As, and Ge. The category includes bandgap, electron mobility, effective mass, and other relevant characteristics.

Step 3: In step 3, statistical methods like Shockley-Read-Hall (SHR), Concentration Dependent Mobility (CONMOB), and Optical Transition Rate (OPTR) are used to look at how the different parts of a solar cell interact with each other again.

Step 4: The acquired material parameters and statistical approaches are theoretically used to estimate the performance of the TJ solar cell. The calculation of parameters such as J_{sc} , V_{oc} , FF , and η is required.

Step 6: Investigate the degradation of electrical parameters by the use of photon irradiation circumstances.

Step 7: It is necessary to recalculate the theoretical parameters (J_{sc} , V_{oc} , FF , etc.) while considering the effects of degradation caused by photon irradiation. Taking this step helps gain knowledge of the influence that external variables have on the functioning of the solar cell.

Step 8: Measure the TJ solar cells' external quantum efficiency (EQE) both before and after proton irradiation. It is feasible to determine the solar cell's efficiency at different wavelengths by using EQE measurements. It is, therefore, possible to use the EQE data to calculate the core parameters (J_{sc} , V_{oc} , FF).

Step 9: The current-voltage (I-V) and power-voltage (P-V) characteristics are calculated to illustrate the behaviour of the solar cell under different conditions.

Result and Discussion

The results of the modelling and simulation study on InGa P/Ga As/Ge triple -junction solar cells indicate that optimising design parameters could significantly enhance performance. Researchers were able to make configurations that were more efficient than standard designs by changing the bandgap energies, doping concentrations, and layer thickness. This optimisation increases the theoretical maximum efficiency and offers valuable insights for practical manufacturing, highlighting the significance of customised design in progressing solar cell technology towards more efficient and commercially viable solutions.

Figure 3 shows that a triple-junction solar cell is composed of three layers of different materials: indium gallium phosphide (InGa P), gallium arsenide (Ga As), and germanium (Ge). Each layer functions as a p-n junction, a region of a semiconductor doped with both p-type and n-type impurities, creating an electric field that enables the conversion of sunlight into electricity. The distinct layers absorb different wavelengths of light, with the InGaP layer capturing the highest-energy photons, the Ga As layer absorbing middle-energy photons, and the Ge layer taking in the lowest-energy photons. This layered structure allows the triple-junction solar cell to convert more sunlight into electricity compared to a single-junction solar cell, significantly enhancing its overall efficiency.

Figure 3: InGaP_GaAs_GeTriple Junction solar cell.

Figure 4 shows the current density versus voltage (J-V) of a solar cell at the National Renewable Energy Laboratory. The x-axis labelled "Voltage (V)" and the y-axis labelled "Current Density (A/cm²)," display several solar cell configurations: "MA," "Ref," "Si HJ," and "Tunnel HJ." The "Ref" cell shows the lowest current density, while the "Tunnel HJ" cell demonstrates higher current density at lower voltages, which could be advantageous for solar cells operating in low-light conditions."

Figure 4 :Solar 3J InGaP_GaAs_Ge tandem Model

Figure 5(a) shows the labelled "External Quantum Efficiency (%)" on the y-axis and "Wavelength (nm)" on the x-axis. It displays the performance of three materials: Indium Gallium Phosphide (InGa P), Gallium Arsenide (Ga As), and Germanium (Ge). Each material has a corresponding line on the graph, with InGa P being the highest, indicating it has the highest external quantum efficiency, converting the most absorbed photons into electricity. Ga As is in the middle, while Ge is the lowest, showing it has the least conversion efficiency. The x-axis spans from 200 to 1800 nanometers, covering a substantial part of the solar spectrum, and the y-axis ranges from 0 to 100%, representing the efficiency of photon-to-electricity conversion for each material.

Figure 5(b) shows the graph plotting "External Quantum Efficiency (%)" on the y-axis against "Wavelength (nm)" on the x-axis. The graph depicts various solar cells, including AM 1.5, 3J solar cells, InGaP, GaAs, and Ge. AM

1.5 represents a standard solar spectrum, while the 3J solar cell likely denotes a triple-junction solar cell, known for the highest light absorption efficiency due to its multiple layers by wavelength (200 nm to 1800 nm). InGaP shows peak efficiency around 500 nm, indicating its proficiency with shorter wavelengths, whereas GaAs perform best around 800 nm, similar to AM 1.5. Ge exhibits lower overall efficiency, with a peak at 1100 nm, demonstrating its specialisation in longer wavelength conversion. These insights highlight how different materials and multi-junction designs impact solar cell efficiency across varying light wavelengths.

(a)

(a)

Figure 5(a): EQE vs wavelength(nm) without 3j solar cell and **(b):** EQE vs wavelength(nm) with 3j solar cell

Figure 6 shows the x-axis labelled "Energy (EF)," where EF denotes the Fermi energy, the energy level at which fermions have a 50% probability of occupation. The y-axis is labelled "probability," indicating the likelihood of fermions occupying an energy state. Multiple curves represent different temperatures (e.g., T1, T2, T3), with higher temperatures showing a broader spread in probability distribution around the Fermi energy. These curves have a unique S-shaped shape that shows how temperature changes the chances of fermions occupying different energy levels compared to the Fermi level.

Figure 6: Fermi distribution

Figure 7 shows plots of intrinsic carrier density against temperature (K), with Germanium (Ge), Gallium Arsenide (Ga As), and Indium Gallium Phosphide (InGa P) represented. All materials show a corresponding increase in electrical conductivity as temperature increases along the x-axis. Indium Gallium Phosphide (InGa P) consistently exhibits the highest conductivity across the temperature range, followed by Gallium Arsenide (Ga As), and then Germanium (Ge), which displays the lowest conductivity. The data indicates that conductivity increases at an accelerating rate with rising temperatures.

Figure 7: Intrinsic carrier density (electrons per cubic cm)

Figure 8 shows an I-V curve representation of the relationship between the electrical current (I) flowing through a solar cell and the voltage (V). The four numbers along the curve, 0.0025, 0.0075, 0.0125, and 0.025, likely represent different power outputs of the solar cell. The “P = 52.4567 mW/cm²,” indicates that the units for these numbers are milliwatts per square centimetre (mW/cm²). This is a power density unit, which is the amount of power produced per unit area. So, the numbers along the curve likely represent the solar cell's power density at different points on the I-V curve. As the voltage applied to the solar cell increases, so does the cell's

current. The curve reaches a maximum point, which is known as the point of maximum power (P_m). After this point, the TJ solar cell shows that the current starts to decrease as the voltage continues to increase.

Figure 8: I-V plot

Figure 9 (a) shows the x-axis is labelled "Temperature (K)" and its values range from 300.00k to 400.00 Kelvin. The y-axis is labelled "J (mA/cm²)" and its values range from 19.25 to 21.00. The red line seems to show values that are consistently higher than the green line. There are markings along the x-axis at 300 K, 325 K, 350 K, and 375 K. The curve increases slightly as the temperature increases.

Figure 9 (b) displays the labels "Temperature (K)" on the x-axis and "Voltage (V)" on the y-axis. The increase is not linear. The voltage starts to level off at around 350 Kelvin and starts to decrease slightly between 375 Kelvin and 400 Kelvin. The figure displays "2.9V" and "2.8V" as the maximum voltages.

(a)

(b)

Figure 9(a)

Figure 10 shows the x-axis is labelled "Voltage (V)" and the y-axis is labelled "Current (A)". It starts at a point on the y-axis where the current is zero and the voltage is zero (0,0). As the voltage applied to the solar cell increases, the current produced by the cell also increases. The curve reaches a maximum point, which is known as the knee point or the point of maximum power (Pm). After the knee point, the current starts to decrease as the voltage continues to increase. This is because the solar cell is no longer able to absorb all of the light energy that is being illuminated up.

Figure 10: Solar cell characteristics

Figure 11(a) shows the x-axis is labelled "Temperature (K)" and shows the temperature in Kelvin. It ranges from 300 Kelvin to 400 Kelvin with markings every 25 Kelvin. The y-axis is labelled "Efficiency (%)" and shows the efficiency of the turbine. It ranges from 30% to 44%. This means that as the temperature increases, the efficiency of the turbine also decreases.

Figure 11(b) shows the x-axis is labelled "Temperature (K)" and the y-axis represents the fill factor in percentage (%). The fill factor decreases consistently as the temperature increases from 300 K to 400 K. The decline appears relatively linear but has a steeper slope between 350 K and 375 K, and 375k to 400k indicating a more rapid decrease in fill factor within this temperature range.

Figure 11(a): Fill factor versus temperature and (b): Fill factor versus temperature

Figure 12(a) shows the X-axis represents the temperature in Kelvin (K). Ranges from 300 K to 400 K, marked at intervals of 25 K. Y-Axis Represents the maximum power density P_{max} in milliwatts per square centimetre (mW/cm^2) which Ranges from $38 mW/cm^2$ to $54 mW/cm^2$, marked at intervals of $2 mW/cm^2$. The maximum power density decreases consistently as the temperature increases from 300 K to 400 K. The decline appears relatively linear, indicating a steady decrease in performance with rising temperature.

Figure 12 (b) shows that the X-axis represents the anode voltage in volts (V). The anode voltage ranges from 0.0 V to 3.5 V, with intervals of 0.5 V. and Y-Axis Represents the output power in milliwatts (mW) and ranges from 0 mW to 60 mW, marked at intervals of 5 mW. The graph indicates that the output power increases with the anode voltage up to a certain point, after which it decreases sharply. The maximum output power achieved is 52.4567 mW at an anode voltage slightly above 2.5 V. There is a significant drop in output power beyond this optimal voltage, suggesting potential limitations or inefficiencies at higher voltages.

Figure 12(a): P_{max} versus temperature and (b): Power vs voltage plot

Table 3 presents various performance parameters of a solar cell at different temperatures that demonstrate the overall impact of temperature on the solar cell's performance parameters.

Table 3: Triple junction solar cell performance with temperature variation.

Parameter	300 K	325 K	350 K	375 K	400 K
V _{oc} (V)	2.868	2.743	2.624	2.502	2.389
J _{sc} (mA/cm ²)	20.45	20.45	20.45	20.45	20.45
V _{max} (V)	2.801	2.705	2.592	2.447	2.168
J _{max} (mA/cm ²)	19.821	19.745	19.627	19.708	19.322
P _{max} (mW/cm ²)	52.4567	49.748	46.632	42.374	39.252
Fill Factor (%)	89.4341	88.6863	86.9014	82.7641	80.3437
Efficiency (%)	41.9653	39.7984	37.3056	33.8992	31.4016

Conclusion

The development of high-efficiency triple-junction solar cells using InGa P/Ga As/Ge materials represents a significant advancement in photovoltaic technology. These cells can capture a wider spectrum of sunlight, leading to improved efficiency. The study emphasizes the influence of various factors on solar cell performance, affecting their electrical output and overall efficiency. For example, as the temperature increases up to 300 K, parameters such as V_{oc} (V), J_{sc} (mA/cm²), V_{max} (V), J_{max} (mA/cm²), P_{max} (mW/cm²), Fill Factor (%), and Efficiency (%) exhibit substantial increases, indicating their sensitivity to thermal conditions. This research marks a major milestone in solar energy technology, offering the potential for enhanced efficiency and sustainability. By optimizing these factors, the study paves the way for ongoing innovation in photovoltaics to meet the growing global demand for energy through more efficient solar power solutions. This research significantly advances solar energy solutions by fostering ongoing innovation in photovoltaics. By optimizing design parameters, it enhances the efficiency and sustainability of solar cells, making solar energy a more viable and widespread option for renewable energy. This contributes to a more sustainable energy landscape.

The future scope of this research could further explore optimizing these parameters to minimize efficiency losses at higher temperatures and improve overall performance. This could involve developing new materials and structures to better manage thermal effects and enhance durability. Additionally, integrating these advanced solar cells into practical applications and scalable production processes would be crucial for widespread adoption. Continued advancements in this field have the potential to significantly contribute to a

more sustainable energy landscape, reducing reliance on fossil fuels and supporting global energy needs with renewable resources.

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